

Enhancing Compressive Strength of Laterite Soil through the Agricultural Waste Material Bamboo Ash Stabilization

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ABSTRACT

All types of soil are used as the ground foundation to support the construction of any structures including roads and buildings. Laterite soil has the properties of cohesive and cohesionless soil. This is because its properties are mostly well-graded including silt, clay, sand, and gravel. However, laterite soil's physical and mechanical properties require improvement. Potential laterite soil used for the construction of roads and development activity is necessary for geotechnical application. Therefore, this research aims to study the performance stability in compressive strength of native laterite soil with bamboo ash (BA). The testing experiments have shown that the behavior of bamboo ash is used to strengthen the laterite soil resulting in the bamboo ash enhancing the performance of laterite formation in ground improvement. In this study, 0%, 5%, 10%, 15%, and 20% bamboo ash content were used to study the effect of BA on native lateritic soils at 0, 3, and 7 days of curing. It is indicated that the strength for 3 curing days increases strength to 8.4% after adding 5% BA. It increases the strength after adding 10%, 15%, and 20% with the percentage of the increments 7.2%, 1.7%, and 0.7%, respectively. In the physical properties results, the specific gravity of soil shows an average of 1.66. As a result, LL and PL have been identified as 29% and 14.1% respectively. Lateritic soil water content measured in this study was 10.84%. Compaction tests identify MDD as 1.807 g/cm³, while OMC content is 13.3%. Lateritic soils are classified as sedimentary sandy soils according to the results of particle distribution soil tests. In the end, the results identified for enhancement of the addition of bamboo ash show a strong increment for lateritic materials. Bamboo ash (BA) appears secondary in large-scale studies. BA reacts as an economical and sustainable treatment material in geotechnical applications.

1. Introduction

Many methods are used for soil improvement. The command method of soil improvement mostly uses soil stabilization. The technique of soil stabilization is employed to improve the engineering properties of soils, including compressive strength, triaxial stress, and consolidation [1]. According to

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Tedla *et al.*, [2] physical properties also are important parameter to the soil stabilization. Both properties making them more suitable for construction purposes. It involves adding stabilizing agents to the soil to improve its strength, durability, and other relevant properties. Compressive strength is a critical parameter in soil mechanics and construction engineering. By improving the compressive strength of soil, it essential can ensuring the stability and longevity of structures built on it.

Residual soil or laterite soil is formed in wet and hot tropical areas. The texture of laterite soil is rusty red due to the iron oxides present in the properties. It is derived from a wide variety of rock weathering conditions. The portion of laterite soil such as in a different type of minerals makes it different from some soil [3]. As mentioned by Joshua *et al.*, [4] the clay mineral is a large portion of the laterite soil. In engineering properties, these characteristics affect the significant portion of laterite soil when applied to the load. For the road, laterite soil is used as the subbases or bases. Yamus *et al.*, [5] also stated that as well as other engineering applications such as embankment filling and road construction. However, natural laterite soil is poor for road construction because it contains some portions that can retain the water. However, due to its tendency to retain water, soil failure occurs because of shrinkage which can show different results in the properties of materials. From the process of laterization, Okonkwo *et al.*, [6] also mentioned that the laterite soil involves the weathering of minerals and rocks over time. This process results in laterite soil containing a high percentage of hydrated halloysite, goethite, or gibbsite which present problems for engineering properties. For engineering purposes, Aderounmu *et al.*, [7] also add it will give properties problems such as affecting pore the shape of pores during the mixing process, because of these characteristics, it increases the risk of the potential to fail when construction activity is active on the top of the soil. According to Oluyemi [8], some lateritic soils have suitable mechanical properties and are commonly used for road applications due to their compatible engineering properties, making them suitable for slope stability, and various constructions. Yusof *et al.*, [9] stated that soil plays a crucial role in facilitating shallow foundation support, constructing dams, creating uniform embankments, ensuring slope stability, and serving as sub-grade material in roads. Treatment and stabilization are the methods that extensively improve the engineering properties of soft materials as mentioned by Md Yusof *et al.*, [10]. Treatment is recommended, but in common applications, stabilization is an active application for on-site construction because of time and cost. Soil stabilization by mixing soil with admixture or other byproduct materials is one of the soil improvement and ground modification techniques. Therefore, an improvement of the soil is needed [11].

Bamboo ash or burning bamboo is a by-product, contains various minerals and compounds that can potentially improve soil properties when used as a stabilizing agent. Bamboo ash has been investigated for its effectiveness in enhancing the properties of different soil types [12]. It has a fine, powdery texture with a light color ranging from grayish white to light gray. As well as it has a porous structure, which can contribute to its ability to interact with soil particles and improve soil properties [13]. Alkaline compounds in the bamboo ash such as potassium oxide and calcium oxide, which have been found to exhibit soil-stabilizing properties. These alkaline compounds can react with clay minerals and organic matter in the soil, leading to changes in soil structure and properties as mentioned by Rangan *et al.*, [14].

In the research from Meshida [15] and Alayaki [16], it stated that soils could not provide the longevity evidenced for road pavements. It is very challenging when used for various earthworks and engineering construction. The presence of clay in laterite soil is one of the reasons for the behavior unfavorably responding to changes in water content [17]. At the same time, the higher content of clay minerals in the laterite soil can reduce the strength. Therefore, reviews of previous researchers identified that using chemical stabilization increases the compressive strength parameters [18]. Furthermore, the use of by-products from industry and chemical admixture can stabilize the soil

particles pozzolanically [19] especially laterite soil stabilized with lime improve the strength of soil two (2) or three (3) times the natural strength of the soil and reduce construction costs can be seen review papers by several authors [20,21].

Mostly in soil stabilization, the material is friendly to users and commonly used as the nature of commercial stabilization additives. The ash is a cheaper alternative to meet the combination of the pozzolanic reaction [22]. By-products are a cost-effective alternative to cementation binding agents for stabilizing soft soil. Cement and lime also performed a good analysis of traditional stabilizers compared to non-traditional stabilizers [23]. Bamboo ash is considered environmentally friendly as it can alter its mechanical and chemical properties, leading to improvements in strength, stability, and permeability. It can help reduce waste and promote sustainable practices in construction and agriculture as it is utilizing bamboo ash in soil stabilization [24].

According to Jayanthi *et al.*, [25] and Gidebo *et al.*, [26], some ash that contains pozzolans such as silicon dioxide (SiO_2) are self-cementing. For example, material from the plantation. A lot of by-product materials from the plantation are used as the materials for the admixture in soil stabilization. It is used to replace chemical stabilization and encourage the usage of environmentally sustainable materials in ground improvement [27]. Bamboo leaf ash, a by-product from bamboo, can serve as a stabilizer to enhance the strength of soft soil. Ongoing research focuses on the utilization of bamboo ash in soil stabilization. The studies always focusing on its effectiveness in different soil types and environmental conditions. Same as other materials, bamboo ash or burning bamboo has been explored for various applications, including road construction, embankment stabilization, erosion control, and agricultural soil improvement. Most important is about the method how its work at site and the results if it apply at site as mentioned by Inim *et al.*, [28].

Bamboo ash (BA) is one of the signs of pozzolanic material due to the presence of silicon dioxide [29]. A material from by-product bamboo or other agriculture materials when mixed with soft soil can be applied as the treatment method to the soft soil [30]. Therefore, this study presents the performance stability of native lateritic soils when mixed with bamboo ash (BA) and reviews the initial performance of a lateritic soil mixture with BA in 0, 3, and 7 days of curing. The results of this study were analyzed and discussed to understand the effect of BA on the laterite soil tested. This alternative was used as an alternative for increasing the engineering characteristics of weak soil for construction.

2. Methodology

The sub-topic methodology explains the methods used in this study which are laterite soil and bamboo ash (BA) in this research. The procedure used in this research is to fulfill the objective which was to observe the effect of engineering characteristics on the performance of mixing bamboo ash (BA) into laterite soil.

2.1 Laterite Soil Sample and Bamboo Ash (BA) Materials

This section discussed the materials used in this study which were laterite soil and bamboo ash (BA). The acquisition of laterite soil from the boreholes was located at Jalan Broga, Semenyih, Selangor ($2^\circ 56' 19.3''$ N, $101^\circ 53' 47.2''$ E) in a section about 0.3 meter to 1 meter depth of ground sampling. The top surface of the soil was removed or cleaned first from any debris or leaves before extracting the sample from a depth of around 0.1 meter to 1 meter. This was done to avoid mixing any debris materials with the soil during extraction. The extraction of the sample was divided into undisturbed and disturbed samples. The sample for undisturbed extraction was extruded properly to

reduce movement during sampling. The sample used as the thin wall sample was then wrapped with plastic, labeled, and kept in a proper container. For the disturbed samples, the soil was randomly extruded, placed in a proper container, and labeled. Both undisturbed and disturbed samples were transported to the laboratory for preparation and testing of physical and mechanical properties. For the bamboo ash (BA) sample, it could either be purchased from NWL Green Enterprise, which is an agricultural supplier from Penang, Malaysia. The other alternative is the original natural bamboo which was collected from the tree and kept under the sun dried for a few days. The sample was oven to 600°C temperature to make it turn into ash. It follows by allowing the bamboo to cool for a few hours and crash it to easily sieved through a 300 µm sieve size to obtain the ash. The ash is sealed and kept in the container to avoid any dry absorption.

2.2 Methods

Several testings for physical properties were determined during this study such as specific gravity, Atterberg limit, proctor (OMC & MDD), water content, and sieving size. The physical properties are the important parameter for the natural soil because they show the natural matter of the characteristics of soil without changing its chemical composition. The changes in soil strength after mixing with bamboo were measured by following the procedure and processes of the testing of unconfined compressive strength (UCS) were determined according to stipulated standard for geotechnical testing [31].

2.2.1 Specific gravity

In this study, ratio of the density was using the standard temperature. The specific gravity represents the ratio of the weight of the materials at the same temperature. The measure of the density of a substance in relation to that of water was determined according to the following geotechnical testing standards [31].

2.2.2 Atterberg limit

In this study, the Atterberg limits were utilized to determine the plastic and liquid limits. The procedures and testing protocols followed the stipulated standard for geotechnical testing. During the liquid limit testing, water content was incrementally added to the soil to transition it from a plastic to a liquid state. It's important to note that soil conditions can evolve over time, transitioning to a semi-solid state as water content changes. The water content for both the plastic and liquid limits was measured over in 24-hours period according to the following geotechnical testing standards [31].

2.2.3 Compaction test

In this study, the process of the proctor machine was according to geotechnical testing standard. Compaction tests are to determine a soil sustains mechanical stress and is densified which are OMC and MDD consist to natural soil. The water amount in the type of sample was used for designing the mixture portion of decomposition when the soil was mixed with the bamboo ash. During the compaction test, the bulk and dry densities were also calculated [31].

2.2.4 Water content

In this study, water content is the crucial parameter that needs to be determined. The calculation of water content follows British Standard 1377: 1990 [31]. According to the standard procedure, the method involves monitoring the quantity of the original natural soil dried in a microwave oven at temperatures ranging from 100 to 110 degrees Celsius.

2.2.5 Sieve analysis

Laterite soil characteristics are cohesive and cohesionless soil. Therefore, it is important the sieve analysis commonly known particle size laterite soil whether it's more to fine or gravels. For the sieve analysis the testing is use sieve machine shaking according to the geotechnical testing procedure. Total of the sample for this experimental works was used at around 1010 g. According to the procedure, the shaker was used for 10 minutes to classify the different sizes by layering sieves with different grade sizes. Soil retained at each sieve was recorded according to the following geotechnical testing standards [31].

2.2.6 Shear strength (stress versus strain)

In this study, shear strength or stress versus strain was determined to identify the maximum shear compressive strength of the sample. The design of the mixing was divided into two (2) types: unstabilized and stabilized soil. Unstabilized samples were used as the reference materials, consisting of samples not mixed with the material binder. These unstabilized samples serve as the reference materials, with a matrix composition for the analysed samples, where the elemental mass fractions are close to the expected ones in the unknown samples. Stabilized soil involved mixing laterite with bamboo ash (BA). The laterite was mixed with bamboo ash (BA) in concentrations of 5%, 10%, 15%, and 20% for curing of 0, 3, and 7 days. The calculation of the design mix shows that 5% BA means adding 0.5g BA for every 100g of wet soil.

3. Results

For the analysis of the results and the elaboration of the results were shown outcomes for the results of samples for stress versus strain (UCS) laboratory works conducted throughout the duration of the study time. Three (3) specimens were conducted to record the average reading of the result. The average of the UCS test shown in Table 1 were the various percentages of bamboo ash (BA) and curing periods (0, 3, and 7 days) with a total number of 39 specimens.

3.1 Specific Gravity

In this study, the results for specific gravity identified in the reading 1.66 from the average of the three (3) specimens. According to Rangan *et al.*, [32], the ratio of the weight of the materials of laterite soil shows an average of 2.7. This result is also supported by Joshua *et al.*, [4] which shows the specific gravity soil in an average of 2.67. In this study, the result was determined to be less than 2.55. The soil sample revealed that the parent materials, primarily composed of quartz and lacking significant laterization, were on average decomposed.

Table 1
 Average UCS value

Label	Laterite soil %	Bamboo ash (BA)%	Average UCS kPa		
			Curing days		
			0	3	7
A	100	-	152.4	-	-
B	95	5	207.3	166.4	182.2
C	90	10	199.9	179.4	189.7
D	85	15	191.0	182.5	168.2
E	80	20	203.3	183.7	223.6

3.2 Atterberg Limit

In this investigation, the mean moisture content (plastic limit) of the lateritic soil samples was determined to be 14.1%. Subsequently, the plastic index for the tested soil yielded a result of 18.45%. This analysis identified that the overall plasticity index falls within the range of 6.11% to 20.59%. According to reference by Joshua *et al.*, [4], the average plasticity index obtained is 21.2%. With a plasticity index surpassing 17%, the soil in this study was classified as highly plastic. The lateritic soil lacking sodium bentonite demonstrated the lowest plastic index value at 6.11%, accompanied by a plastic limit of 59.52% and a liquid limit of 53.41%, classifying it as intermediate plasticity silt, denoted as MI.

3.3 Compaction Test

This study involved plotting the water content curve against dry density to determine the maximum dry density (MDD) and maximum optimum moisture content (OMC) of natural lateritic soil. The MDD was found to be 1.807 g/cm³, while the OMC was determined to be 13.3%. During experimentation, water contents of 5%, 10%, and 15% were utilized, with the average soil mass and volume for the three specimens recorded at 1746 g and 976.9 cm³, respectively. The OMC result falls within the range of moisture content typical for natural lateritic soil, aligning closely with findings from previous research [4].

3.4 Water Content

In this study, three samples were taken to determine the water content. However, the average result taken for the water content test was 10.84%. Based on studies by Joshua *et al.*, [4] and Yamusa *et al.*, [30], the water content for laterite soil was in the range of 20.5% and 34%. However, the results of the water content in this study were determined to be lower than in the previous study. Therefore, it is needed to consider the different sample locations and weather conditions during the extraction of the sample. Furthermore, the storing method and procedure were also crucial in preventing the natural water content evaporating.

3.5 Sieve Size Analysis

In the sieve size analysis, the results were 14.96%, the percentage of sand is 81.9%, and the percentage of silt is 3.17%. The values of D₁₀, D₃₀, and D₆₀ were 0.2 mm, 0.63 mm, and 1.32 mm, respectively. While the value of the C_u was 6.6, C_c was between 0.5 to 3. In this study, the sample laterite soil samples are categorized as good-grade sand. According to Yamusa *et al.*, [30], the

percentage of soil passing sieve no. 200 is 30%. Whereas according to Joshua *et al.*, [4], the percentage of land passing sieve no. 200 is an average of 92.99%. As a result of the sieve size in this study, the percentage of soil passing sieve no. 200 is 3.14% which is a significant difference from previous studies. Since the lateritic soil in this study was classified as good-grade sand, it had more particles larger than sieve no. 200 resulting in the percentage of soil that passes through filter no. 200 during filter analysis.

3.6 Unconfined Compressive Strength (UCS) Test

Figure 1 represents sample A – laterite soil only. Three (3) specimens were carried out from sample A namely specimens 1, 2, and 3. The water content used was 13.3% and the strength results for 0 curing days show that sample label specimen 2 achieves a strength of 163.8 kN/m², which is a higher value when compared with sample label specimen 1 reaches a strength of 136.4 kN/m² and specimen 3 reaches strength 157.1 kN/m². Based on Figure 1, the values of three (3) specimens are slightly different and the average value of the strength is 152.4 kN/m². According to Inim *et al.*, [28] various factors encourage the strength of the soil such as the physical properties. The soil itself gives the difference in strength between the specimens even if it is taken from the same sample.

Figure 2 represents sample B – Laterite + 5% BA for 0 days. Instead of the label B (0 days), indicate the compressive strength for laterite soil composition of 5% BA sample at 0 curing day. Three (3) specimens were carried out from samples B – laterite + 5% BA for 0 days, namely as specimens 1, 2, and 3. Also, from Figure 2, the strength results for laterite + 5% BA, 0 curing day show that specimen 2 reaches a strength of 220.8 kN/m² which is the highest value compared to specimens 1 and 3. Specimens 1 and 3 reach the strength of 200.2 kN/m² and 200.9 kN/m² respectively and the average value of the strength is 207.3 kN/m². According to Ishak *et al.*, [29] the presence of the additives or stabilizers material change the strength of the soil. The stabilizer material is important in engineering applications, as it can influence the performance of structure on or with such soil compositions.

Fig. 1. Strength for the control sample at 0-day curing

Fig. 2. Strength for the laterite + 5% BA sample at 0-day curing

Figure 3 represents sample B – laterite + 5% BA for 3 days. Instead of the label B (3 days), indicate compressive strength for laterite soil composition 5% BA sample at 3 curing days. Three (3) specimens were carried out from samples B – laterite + 5% BA for 3 days, namely specimens 1, 2, and 3. Also, from Figure 3, the strength results for laterite + 5% BA, 3 curing days show that specimen 3 reaches a strength of 176.6 kN/m² which is the slightly maximum value compared with specimen 1 and specimen 2. Specimens 1 and 2 reach the strength of 164.4 kN/m² and 158.2 kN/m² respectively and the average value of the strength is 166.4 kN/m². As mentioned by Ikeagwuani *et al.*, [13] the average

value provides a summary of overall strength of the laterite soil sample at the given water content and curing condition. Therefore, conducting more experimental works and computing the average results helps in obtaining a more representative understanding of the soil's strength properties.

Figure 4 represents sample B – laterite + 5% BA for 7 days. Instead of the label B (7 days), indicate compressive strength for laterite soil composition 5% BA sample at 7 curing days. Three (3) specimens were carried out from samples B – laterite + 5% BA for 7 days, namely specimens 1, 2, and 3. Also, from Figure 4, the strength results for laterite + 5% BA, 7 curing days show that specimen 2 reaches a strength of 205.5 kN/m² which is the slightly maximum value compared with specimen 1 and specimen 3. Specimens 1 and 3 reach the strength of 177.3 kN/m² and 163.8 kN/m² respectively and the average value of the strength is 182.2 kN/m². These differences could be due to factors such as variations in the curing conditions, hydration processes, and the interaction between bamboo ash additives and the laterite soil. According to Inim *et al.*, [28], it is observed that there is a decrease in average strength over the curing period. This decrease could be attributed to factors such as consolidation of the soil, changes in moisture stresses within the specimens as they undergo curing.

Fig. 3. Strength for the Laterite + 5% BA sample at 3-day curing

Fig. 4. Strength for the Laterite + 5% BA sample at 7-day curing

Figure 5 represents sample C – laterite + 10% BA for 0 days. Instead of the label C (0 days), indicate compressive strength for laterite soil composition 10% BA sample at 0 curing day. Three (3) specimens were carried out from samples C – laterite + 10% BA for 0 days, namely specimens 1, 2, and 3. Also, from Figure 5, the strength results for laterite + 10% BA, 0 curing days show that specimen 1 reaches a strength of 214.8 kN/m² which is the slightly maximum value compared with specimen 2 and specimen 3. Specimens 2 and 3 reach the strength of 187.1 kN/m² and 197.7 kN/m² respectively and the average value of the strength is 199.9 kN/m². It is observed that the higher percentage of bamboo ash in sample C did not result in higher average strength at this curing stage. average strength at this. As mentioned by Ikeagwuani *et al.*, [13] this could be several factors such as the optimal percentage of bamboo ash for enhancing soil strength, the distribution of the additive within the soil matrix, and the physical properties of the soil.

Figure 6 represents sample C – laterite + 10% BA for 3 days. Instead of the label C (3 days), indicate compressive strength for laterite soil composition 10% BA sample at 3 curing days. Three (3) specimens were carried out from samples C – laterite + 10% BA for 3 days, namely specimens 1, 2, and 3. Also, from Figure 6, the strength results for laterite + 10% BA, 3 curing days shows that specimen 1 reaches a strength of 203.4 kN/m² which is the slightly maximum value compared with specimen 2 and specimen 3. Specimens 2 and 3 reach the strength of 181 kN/m² and 153.9 kN/m² respectively and the average value of the strength is 179.4 kN/m². Understanding the changes of the

strength in the curing period is crucial for assessing the long-term performance and stability of the structures and the soil conditions as mentioned by Ishak *et al.*, [29].

Fig. 5. Strength for the Laterite + 10% BA sample at 0-day curing

Fig. 6. Strength for the Laterite + 10% BA sample at 3-day curing

Figure 7 represents sample C – Laterite + 10% BA for 7 days. Instead of the label C (7 days), indicate compressive strength for laterite soil composition 10% BA sample at 7 curing days. Three (3) specimens were carried out from samples C – Laterite + 10% BA for 7 days, namely specimens 1, 2, and 3. Also, from Figure 7, the strength results for laterite + 10% BA, 7 curing days show that specimen 3 reaches a strength of 195.5 kN/m² which is the slightly maximum value compared with specimen 1 and specimen 2. Specimens 1 and 2 reach the strength of 188.7 kN/m² and 185.1 kN/m² respectively and the average value of the strength is 189.7 kN/m². Similar to the previous samples, there are slight variations in the strength values among the three specimens of sample C at curing 7 days. The average provides a summary of the measurement of the overall strength of the laterite soil with bamboo ash additives after 7 days of curing. Ishak *et al.*, [29] stated that the strength over time assessing the performance and stability of the structures on the soil. Furthermore, the additional of percentage bamboo ash increased the soil strength and were optimizing soil stabilization techniques in engineering applications. There would be more focus on the evaluating of effectiveness of various types of materials and their optimal concentration of the percentages to achieve desire soil strength.

Figure 8 represents sample D – laterite + 15% BA for 0 days. Instead of the label D (0 days), indicate compressive strength for laterite soil composition 15% BA sample at 0 curing days. Three (3) specimens were carried out from samples D – laterite + 15% BA for 0 days, namely specimens 1, 2, and 3. Also, from Figure 8, the strength results for laterite + 15% BA, 0 curing days show that specimen 1 reaches a strength of 195.4 kN/m² which is the slightly maximum value compared with specimen 2 and specimen 3. Specimens 2 and 3 reach the strength of 196 kN/m² and 185.1 kN/m² respectively and the average value of the strength is 191.0 kN/m². Ishak *et al.*, [29] stated that the strength over time assessing the performance and stability of the structures on the soil. Ikeagwuani *et al.*, [13] stated that the distribution additive in the soil matrix could change the properties.

Figure 9 represents sample D – laterite + 15% BA for 3 days. Instead of the label D (3 days), indicate compressive strength for laterite soil composition 15% BA sample at 3 curing days. Three (3) specimens were carried out from samples D – laterite + 15% BA for 3 days, namely specimens 1, 2, and 3. Also, from Figure 9, the strength results for laterite + 15% BA, 3 curing days show that specimen 1 reaches a strength of 214.2 kN/m² which is the slightly maximum value compared with specimen 2 and specimen 3. Specimens 2 and 3 reach the strength of 144.1 kN/m² and 189.4 kN/m² respectively and the average value of the strength is 182.5 kN/m². As shown in the previous samples, there are some variations in the strength values among the three specimens of sample D at 3 curing days.

Ikeagwuani *et al.*, [13] stated the interaction between additives in the soil matrix related to specimen preparation.

Figure 10 represents sample D – laterite + 15% BA for 7 days. Instead of the label D (7 days), indicate compressive strength for laterite soil composition 15% BA sample at 7 curing days. Three (3) specimens were carried out from samples D – laterite + 15% BA for 7 days, namely specimens 1, 2, and 3. Also, from Figure 10, the strength results for laterite + 15% BA, 7 curing days show that specimen 2 reaches a strength of 195.7 kN/m² which is the slightly maximum value compared with specimen 1 and specimen 3. Specimens 1 and 3 reach the strength of 172.8 kN/m² and 136.2 kN/m² respectively and the average value of the strength is 168.2 kN/m². It is shown that there is evidence that there is a decrease in average strength over the additional curing period. As mentioned by Ishak *et al.*, [29], the development of internal stresses within the specimens as they undergo prolonged curing.

Fig. 7. Strength for the Laterite + 10% BA sample at 7-day curing

Fig. 8. Strength for the laterite + 15% BA sample at 0-day curing

Fig. 9. Strength for the Laterite + 15% BA sample at 3-day curing

Fig. 10. Strength for the Laterite + 15% BA sample at 7-day curing

Figure 11 represents sample E – laterite + 20% BA for 0 days. Instead of the label E (0 days), indicate compressive strength for laterite soil composition 20% BA sample at 0 curing days. Three (3) specimens were carried out from samples E – laterite + 20% BA for 0 days, namely specimens 1, 2, and 3. Also, from Figure 11, the strength results for laterite + 20% BA, 0 curing days shows that specimen 1 reaches a strength of 224.5 kN/m² which is the slightly maximum value compared with specimen 2 and specimen 3. Specimens 2 and 3 reach the strength of 201.5 kN/m² and 184.0 kN/m²

respectively and the average value of the strength is 203.3 kN/m^2 . As observed in the previous samples, there are discernible variations in the strength values among the three specimens of sample E at 0 curing days. As stated by Ikeagwuani *et al.*, [13] the impact of bamboo ash especially when conducting the experimental works in systematic give more valuable in terms of their achievement desire in soil strength.

Figure 12 represents sample E – laterite + 20% BA for 3 days. Instead of the label E (3 days), indicate compressive strength for laterite soil composition 20% BA sample at 3 curing days. Three (3) specimens were carried out from samples E – laterite + 20% BA for 3 days, namely specimens 1, 2, and 3. Also, from Figure 12, the strength results for laterite + 20% BA, 3 curing days show that specimen 3 reaches a strength of 191.2 kN/m^2 which is the slightly maximum value compared with specimen 1 and specimen 2. Specimens 1 and 2 reach the strength of 185.6 kN/m^2 and 174.4 kN/m^2 respectively and the average value of the strength is 183.7 kN/m^2 . Comparing the average strength values of sample E at 3 curing days with the average strength values of sample E at 0 days, it is show that there is a decrease in average strength over the additional curing period. According to Inim *et al.*, [28], experimental works at different curing times and analyzing the results, gaining insights into the behavior of the soil and its reactions cementations processes.

Fig. 11. Strength for the Laterite + 20% BA sample at 0-day curing

Fig. 12. Strength for the Laterite + 20% BA sample at 3-day curing

Figure 13 represents sample E –laterite + 20% BA for 7 days. Instead of the label E (7 days), indicate compressive strength for laterite soil composition 20% BA sample at 7 curing days. Three (3) specimens were carried out from samples E – laterite + 20% BA for 7 days, namely specimens 1, 2, and 3. Also, from Figure 13, the strength results for laterite + 20% BA, 7 curing days show that specimen 2 reaches a strength of 243.1 kN/m^2 which is the slightly maximum value compared with specimen 1 and specimen 3. Specimens 1 and 3 reach the strength of 189.2 kN/m^2 and 238.5 kN/m^2 respectively and the average value of the strength is 223.6 kN/m^2 . Comparing the average values of sample E at 7 curing days with the average strength values of sample E at 0 days, the strength shows an increase strength over the curing period. Inim *et al.*, [28], also add the experimental works at different curing times and analyzing the results, gaining insights into the behavior of the soil and its reactions cementations processes.

Finally in Figure 14, compressive strength value for laterite soil in 0% of binder when mixture the bamboo ash (BA) is 152.4 kN/m^2 . After adding the 5% BA for 0 curing days, achieved strength 207.3 kN/m^2 , difference within 26.5%. After adding 10% BA, the strength decreased to 199.9 kN/m^2 which is a 3.6% reduction, and slightly decreased 4.5% (191 kN/m^2) after adding 15% BA. However, the strength starts to increase to 203.3 kN/m^2 which is a 6.1% increment after adding 20% BA. Also, from Figure 14, it is indicated that the strength for 3 curing days achieves 166.4 kN/m^2 after adding 5% BA

and the strength increases to 8.4%. It continuously increases the strength (179.4 kN/m², 182.5 kN/m², and 183.7 kN/m²) after adding 10%, 15%, and 20% with the percentage of the increments 7.2%, 1.7%, and 0.7% respectively. These results show that bamboo ash has a significant impact on the compressive strength. It is notable that the increase of strength for a certain percentage of bamboo shows a slight decrease before observing another increase in strength at higher bamboo ash. The curing time is generally increasing with longer curing periods.

In Figure 14 also show that the strength continuously increases to 182.2 kN/m² at 7 days after adding 5% BA (16.4% increase the strength). It increases the strength (189.7 kN/m²) to 4% after adding 10% BA before slightly reducing (168.2 kN/m²) to 11% after adding 15% BA. However, the strength (223.6 kN/m²) increases to 25% after adding 20% BA. The bamboo ash powder reacts performance of characteristics laterite soil with good achieve. The mentioned studies by Agate *et al.*, [33] and Peng *et al.*, [34] support the findings, indicating that the reactions of the bamboo ash with soil show the pozzolanic nature reactivity increased with time and temperature. This indicates that the pozzolanic reaction between bamboo ash and laterite soil likely contributes to the observed improvements in compressive strength, especially with longer curing periods [35].

Fig. 13. Strength for the Laterite + 20% BA sample at 7-day curing

Fig. 14. Average strength value for all samples

4. Conclusions

This research investigates the stability of compressive strength in native soil when mixed with bamboo ash (BA) at varying percentages, followed by curing periods of 0, 3, and 7 days. The effect of bamboo ash (BA) on lateritic soil was examined using the UCS test. Additionally, specific gravity, liquid limit, and plastic limit of the lateritic soils were determined, with average specific gravity recorded at 1.66, liquid limit at 29%, and plastic limit at 14%. Compaction tests were conducted to determine optimum moisture content and density, resulting in a maximum dry density of 1.807 g/cm³ and a maximum optimum moisture content of 13.3%. The average water content of the lateritic soil in this study was measured at 10.84%. Based on sieve analysis tests and discussions, the studied lateritic soils are classified as well-graded sandy soils. The addition of bamboo ash led to a significant increase in strength, with the higher value reaching approximately 25%.

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